

Living Lab

Harmonization Guidelines

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Health and Wellbeing
Living Lab Infrastructure

Project Acronym: **VITALISE**

Project Title: Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

Project Number: 101007990

Topic: **Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme
INFRAIA-02-2020
Integrating Activities for Starting Communities**

Type of Action: **RIA - Research and Innovation action**

Start date of the Project: **April 2021**

Duration of the Project: **36 months**

doi: **10.5281/zenodo.10975205**

D4.6 Living Lab Guidelines (final version)

(Version 3.0, 31/3/2024)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Deliverable: D4.6 Living Lab Guidelines (final version)

Work Package: WP4

Due Date: 31 March 2024

Submission Date: 31 March 2024

Lead Beneficiary: ENoLL

Version: 3.0

Status: Submitted

Author name(s): Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Teemu Santonen (LAUREA), Koen Vervoort (ENoLL), Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL), Giulia Campodonico (ENoLL), Martina Desole (ENoLL), Panagiotis Bamidis (AUTH), Silia Petronikolou (AUTH)

Contributor(s): ThessAHALL, LiCalab, Laurea, MindLab, Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab, GAIA Living Lab, LifeSTech, McGill UdeM CRIR, AIT

Reviewer(s): Kim Helsen (LICALAB) Eniko Nagy (TREBAG)

Approved by: Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Project Coordinator

Keywords: Innovation, master course, Living Lab innovation

Nature: R - Report P - Prototype
 D - Demonstrator O - Other

Dissemination level: PU - Public
 CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
 RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

The VITALISE Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TECNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	6/2/2024	ENoLL	Initial version – Table of contents
0.2	12/2/2024	ENoLL, AUTH, LAUREA	Restructure and first input on KPIs
0.3	1/3/2024	AUTH, LAUREA	Changes in introduction and section 3
0.4	4/3/2024	LAUREA	Integrate input for Harmonization framework
1.0	21/3/2024	ENoLL, AUTH, LAUREA	Version ready for internal review
2.0	29/3/2024	LICALAB, TREBAG, ENoLL	Version after review
3.0	31/3/2024	ENoLL	Version approved by the coordinator

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 The VITALISE Project	9
1.2 Purpose and Benefits of Living Lab Harmonization	9
1.3 The Harmonization Process During VITALISE	10
1.4 How to Use this Document	11
2 HARMONIZATION GUIDELINES - TEEMU	12
2.1 The Living Lab Harmonization Framework	13
2.2 Living Lab Lexicon	14
2.3 Living Lab Research Process	14
2.4 Living Lab Innovation Process	16
2.5 Living Lab Governance And Business Model	16
2.6 R&D Services	17
2.7 Data Collection Approaches	17
2.8 Living Lab Research Infrastructure	17
3 HARMONIZATION TOOLS	18
3.1 Self-Assessment Tool	19
3.2 The Living Lab Harmonization Wiki	20
3.3 Panel Management Tool - The Panelab	20
3.4 Public Information on Living Lab Research Infrastructure	20
3.5 Customer Acquisition Tool - Accelup	21
3.6 Taxonomy to Categorizes the Digital Data Collection and Intervention Tools	21
3.7 Data Discovery Repository	21
3.8 Scaling Up Within the Enoll Network	22
3.8.1 Living Lab Harmonization Working Group	22
3.8.2 Scaling Up Across Domains	22
3.8.3 Implementation of KPIs	22
5 CONCLUSIONS	24

Abbreviations

ENoLL EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS

WG WORKING GROUP

Executive Summary

The proposed Harmonization framework aims to standardize common elements of Living Labs, initially focusing on the Health and Wellbeing domain. It seeks consensus among stakeholders to create coherence while allowing flexibility to accommodate differences, aiming for compatibility, interoperability, quality, and the removal of collaboration barriers. The framework identifies common operational elements, creates terminology, and categorizes implementation levels to facilitate dissemination, exploitation of results, and the creation of new business and collaboration opportunities. The harmonization process involves the Harmonization Body, Harmonization Board, and crowdsourcing public opinions through the Living Lab Harmonization wiki page. These entities contribute to the creation of a comprehensive framework for Living Lab operations, reviewed and updated every six months.

This document targets Living Lab practitioners, researchers, and professionals familiar with Living Lab concepts, aiming to align their operations with the harmonization framework for enhanced collaboration. It also serves researchers unfamiliar with Living Lab methodologies but interested in utilizing their services. The document outlines the Harmonization Framework, developed tools by VITALISE, and sustainability through uptake from the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need **1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of participants in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.**

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE facilitates the effective and convenient access to Living Lab Infrastructures by co-creating a Harmonization framework with and for the Living Lab and Research community. This framework has been implemented and tested in three Joint Research Activities across the VITALISE Consortium Living Labs and also in Research studies performed by external researchers in 17 Living Labs research infrastructures during the Transnational Access activities.

1.2. Purpose and Benefits of Living Lab Harmonization

The proposed Harmonization framework aims to provide the tools and definitions of common elements of Living Labs, starting with the Health and Wellbeing domain. The establishment of a consensus-seeking framework aimed at creating coherence, allowing more flexibility and adaptation to accommodate differences when compared to standardization. The key objectives of living lab harmonization include the establishment of compatibility, interoperability, quality and the removal of collaboration barriers among Living Lab stakeholders. Starting with identifying the common operational elements across Living Labs, the harmonization framework creates a terminology and the categorization in various implementation levels (e.g., devices used, offered services, stakeholders) that supports the dissemination and exploitation of results to wider audiences and creating new business and collaboration opportunities. This leads to an open and synergistic ecosystem for innovation and collaboration across the living lab community.

Due to globalization, there is an increasing need to develop innovative solutions that are ready for global markets from the start, as well as to scale up existing domestic solutions to global markets. To address this need, the long-term goal for the living lab community has been to establish a connected and transnational research infrastructure for fostering user-centric innovations in different domains.

1. INTRODUCTION

A transnational living lab network, by definition, denotes collaboration among a group of living labs located and operating in more than one country. Currently, collaboration within the transnational living lab network is characterized by a limited amount of coordinated efforts, which occur at the project level and have a relatively short-term scope (e.g., project duration) (Santonen et al., 2020).

To foster more in-depth collaboration, synchronized efforts, and well-characterized, standardized, documented, and validated processes and services are needed. By adopting a harmonized way of working as suggested by the VITALISE project, the living lab community can take a major step towards becoming the leading European Research Infrastructure for human and user-centric innovations.

1.3. The Harmonization process during VITALISE

Figure 1. The Harmonization process

Two main decision-making actors in VITALISE Harmonization activities were the Harmonization Body, the Harmonization Board. The collection of public opinions through the Living Lab Harmonization wiki page was also a main source of feedback.

The **Harmonization Body** is a community of diverse stakeholders that was created through an open call, having as a primary objective to participate and contribute to the creation of a harmonized framework for Living Lab operations. Through structured discussions, engagement in harmonization events, and active participation in shaping harmonized procedures and services, members contributed to the development of a comprehensive framework for Living Lab operations.

The **Harmonization Board** is a group of Living Labs and Harmonisation experts that were meticulously selected to serve as the decision board for the Living Lab Harmonisation framework. They were meeting every six months, in order to review the results of the harmonisation activities and approve their inclusion to the next version of the harmonisation framework.

The decision-making process was also complemented by crowdsourcing public opinions through the **Living Lab Harmonization wiki page** ([Section 3.2.](#)).

1.4. How to use this document

TO WHOM IS ADDRESSED: This document is intended for Living Lab practitioners, researchers, and professionals who are already acquainted with the Living Lab concept and methodologies and seek to streamline and align their operations with the Living Lab harmonization framework to enhance collaboration with other Living Labs. It can also serve researchers who are unfamiliar with Living Lab concepts and methodologies but are interested in utilizing Living Lab services for their research (Living Lab Research Infrastructures).

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT: This document consolidates and summarizes the various methods, tools, services and outcomes of the VITALISE Living Lab Harmonization Framework, serving as a foundational resource for understanding its implementation, its scope and purpose in each case. More specifically:

SECTION 1 (THIS SECTION)	SECTION 2	SECTION 3	SECTION 4
presents the purpose of this document and how it can be used	presents the overall Harmonization Framework, explaining what information is included in the seven key elements	presents the developed tools that are developed by VITALISE and can assist Living Labs to operate in a harmonized way	presents the sustainability of the harmonization framework through its uptake within the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)

2. HARMONIZATION GUIDELINES

2. HARMONIZATION GUIDELINES

2.1. The Living Lab Harmonization Framework

The *Figure 2* presents the seven key elements of Living Lab Harmonization Framework consisting of: **1) Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)**, **2) Living Lab Governance and Business Model**, **3) Research process**, **4) Innovation process**, **5) R&D Services**, **6) Data collection approaches including a) methods and tools, b) devices and technologies and c) validated questionnaires and instruments** and **7) Living Lab research infrastructure**.

Figure 2. The Living Lab Harmonization Framework

For Living Lab practitioners and researchers, the Harmonization Framework provides a systematic and holistic way to understand living labs as an innovation ecosystem entity. The framework can be used as a foundation that guides research, analysis, and decision-making. It also serves as a map to gain a clear and structured understanding of the various underlying internal and external factors that will impact Living Labs.

2.2. Living Lab Lexicon

The Living Lab Lexicon is a compilation of commonly used words and their definitions within the living lab community. This lexicon serves as a valuable resource for helping students and newcomers understand and master living lab terminology. Adopting a common vocabulary enables effective and precise communication, fostering knowledge sharing by reducing ambiguity. It ensures that practitioners and customers within the field understand each other accurately.

2.3. Living Lab Research Process

The research process focuses on describing the key steps and services needed to acquire, plan, and execute a living lab research project. These steps include 1) customer acquisition, 2) detailed project planning, 3) project implementation and dissemination phases, and 4) innovation ecosystem orchestration. The process also visualizes the linkages between different services to understand input and output feeds. These process descriptions can serve as a guidance map and planning tool when seeking to improve operational performance and quality. Furthermore, customer touchpoints will help tailor marketing, communication and operations for different types of customer needs.

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION AND DISSEMINATION

DETAILED PROJECT PLANNING

CUSTOMER ACQUISITION

TOUCHPOINTS

2.4. Living Lab Innovation Process

The innovation process defines the various phases of the innovation management process that take place during the living lab project. The description of the innovation process aids in evaluating the maturity of the developed solutions and provides suggestions for achieving exploratory and confirmatory research aims. The adoption of the commonly accepted Technology Readiness Level (TRL) framework helps align and communicate Living Lab activities in an easily understandable way to customers and other stakeholders involved in a Living Lab project.

2.5. Living Lab Governance and Business Model

Living lab governance and business model provide a systematic view to understand how living labs operate, seamlessly combining research, development, and innovation processes. It covers the qualifications to become a living lab and defines Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at macro-, meso-, and micro-levels (i.e., living lab ecosystem, project, and activities). Together, these elements can be used to improve the operational quality of the living lab by conducting gap analysis. Furthermore, setting strategic goals or developing a living business plan will greatly benefit from using the Living Lab governance and business model as a starting point.

2.6. R&D services

R&D services include descriptions of common R&D services that living labs offer to their customers, as well as the back-office and supporting services required for delivering these R&D services. Commonly understood R&D services are a fundamental requirement for living labs to open their services to external customers. Without services, there are no customers. Service descriptions can also be used as a tool to compare living labs' service portfolios and to gain an understanding of the types of services living labs offer when developing your own living lab service portfolio.

2.7. Data collection approaches

Data collection approaches include (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies, and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This section provides an understanding of practical data collection approaches currently used by living labs in health and wellbeing settings. The use of common tools and devices for data collection enables better comparability, quality, interoperability, efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and replication. Harmonized data collection approaches serve as a foundation to produce standard reports and improve interoperability between different living labs and research projects. Collaboration becomes easier and helps generate an open dataset with common data elements. The identified data collection approaches are suggested for use when defining research protocols for living lab studies.

2.8. Living lab Research Infrastructure

Living Lab Research Infrastructure is means to deliver and implement all the previous elements and the local innovation ecosystem in which the living lab operates. It defines what a research infrastructure is and the types of research infrastructure environments that currently exist in living labs. Furthermore, it explains the difference of providing excellence-driven, market-driven and wide access for researchers and other customers. Understanding the different variations of living labs and the key characteristics of research infrastructure will help position living labs and create a roadmap for becoming certified research infrastructure.

3. HARMONIZATION TOOLS

3.1. Self-assessment Tool

Living Lab evaluations by ENoLL takes place in the following three levels:

- **Macro-level** focusing on living lab as an organization in a innovation ecosystem,
- **Meso-level** focusing on innovation projects and activities carried out by living lab and,
- **Micro-level** focusing on methodologies and the tools used by Living Lab.

Macro-, meso- and micro-level questions are classified into 6 main chapters (building blocks) which in total includes 15 criteria (supported by the 34 KPIs) for sustainable Living Lab.

Strategy dimension includes governance, business model and collaboration viewpoints. Operations focuses on the operational (project) capabilities, availability of human resources, equipment and infrastructure resources.

Openness covering how open innovation principles within partnerships and innovation process are followed while ensuring transparency and fair ownership of results.

User and reality dimension evaluate the extent of influence users have, their real life contexts and the different ways of user engagement.

Impact & Value creation covers the tangible and intangible value outcomes and their impact to participants, Living Lab and society in general.

Stability & harmonization focuses on how viable the Living Lab currently is and looks at the plans for the future. Next to this it evaluates the adoption level of harmonized living lab procedures.

After the validation of the harmonized set of general Living Lab KPIs, a self-assessment tool for Living Labs was co-created based on these harmonized general Living Lab KPI. This self-assessment tool consists of a set of quantitative questions to collect data around the KPIs in a user-friendly way via an online platform.

3. HARMONIZATION TOOLS

This self-assessment tool is integrated into the application and value capturing processes of ENoLL. Organizations applying to the ENoLL network complete this harmonized quantitative self-assessment before answering to a qualitative application form, also based on the same general Living Lab KPIs. Next to this the self-assessment tool is used as an instrument to benchmark current members of the ENoLL network.

3.2. The Living Lab Harmonization Wiki

The Living Lab Harmonization wiki¹ aims to present and make publicly available the Harmonized processes, services, tools and methods. The wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. It is a wiki like page that targets on enhanced collaboration providing the opportunity to every visitor to annotate a piece of text and provide comments on the corresponding text. The information presented in the wiki was updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section of the wiki, the visitor can find when and by which each version is approved (e.g., "Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX".)

3.3. Panel Management tool - The Panelab

Panelab² is a powerful community management tool designed to streamline the operations of living labs, facilitating seamless communication, data management, and collaboration among stakeholders. By providing a centralized hub for information sharing and project management, Panelab empowers living labs to efficiently coordinate research activities, engage with participants, and collect and analyse data. The platform caters to the specific needs of living labs, enabling them to efficiently manage their panel. Ultimately, the aim of Panelab is to enhance the effectiveness and impact of living labs by providing them with the tools and support they need to drive innovation, foster collaboration and address real-world challenges in diverse domains.

3.4. Public Information on Living Lab Research Infrastructure

The Panelab³ allows each Living Lab to expose its Research Infrastructures and related information to the general public. A Research Infrastructure can include its location, areas of work, and any services offered. Public Research Infrastructures are also available on the EOSC Marketplace so that they may be used by potential researchers who may want to conduct experiments in real environments.

¹ wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com

² app.thepanelab.com

³ app.thepanelab.com/public-infrastructures

3.5. Customer Acquisition Tool - Accelup

Accelup provides a common space where ideas can connect, and businesses can collaborate with the best Living Lab Research Infrastructures to get wider, simplified and efficient access to optimal research on demand services. It is a freelance marketplace website that allows potential employers such as companies, academia, or public actors to post jobs in the form of projects that ENoLL certified Living Labs can then bid to complete. Accelup is tailored to address the research-on-demand needs of any user or Living Labs while offering a transparent bidding process.

3.6. Taxonomy to categorizes the digital data collection and intervention tools

The three-level taxonomy for the digital data collection and intervention tools employed in Health and Wellbeing Living Lab research studies includes 53 subitems across 10 categories. The creation of a taxonomy⁴ supports the effective access to Living Lab Research Infrastructure, and effective data collection and exploitation for enhanced collaboration. Living Labs can use the classification to communicate their technical device portfolio for their customer and compare their existing equipment against other Living Labs. It can also be used to search easily and effectively for the data and devices that are provided by each Living Lab and best fit to each study.

3.7. Data discovery repository

The RAI technical infrastructure is a set of digital tools built and integrated for LLs data leverage and Open Access data processing. The RAI solution is available as a stand-alone solid interface to connect technological stakeholders, offering software solutions to integrate and harmonize LL-produced data, to implement federate data management and to perform open access data processing through the RAI Nodes deployment, to allow data processing persistency and verification of research analysis consistency and integrity through blockchain registration, among others. At the core of the system is the Discovery Portal, a platform to provide a centralized user experience and designed within the scope of the VITALISE project to potentiate metadata discovery across LLs. Built upon robust and established technology, this platform streamlines the process of searching, accessing, and leveraging comprehensive metadata from diverse LL environments worldwide through a user-friendly interface and powerful search capabilities. Exploring the Discovery Portal metadata catalogue, Researchers can identify relevant datasets for their studies, uncovering valuable insights and facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration. Accessible to a wide range of stakeholders and encompassing various domains, including healthcare, the Discovery Portal has the capabilities to cater diverse needs and interests. Overall, the value proposition of the RAI solution lies in the capability to accomplish federated data management by LLs in compliance with data protection policies, while simultaneously offering a democratize access to valuable metadata to a broad range of stakeholders, fostering knowledge exchange, cooperation, innovation, and sustainable development across LL ecosystems network.

⁴ D. Petsani, T. Santonen, B. Merino-Barbancho, G. Epelde, P. Bamidis, E. Konstantinidis, Categorizing digital data collection and intervention tools in health and wellbeing living lab settings: A modified Delphi study, International Journal of Medical Informatics (2024), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2024.105408>

3.8. Scaling up within the ENoLL network

3.8.1. Living Lab Harmonization Working Group

The Living Lab Harmonization Working Group (WG) is established within the ENoLL network in order to continue the Harmonization work that has started in VITALISE. Harmonization is a dynamic process that should be continuously adapted to the current needs and priorities of the Living Lab work. The WG will continue drafting, reviewing, approving, and publishing the new Harmonization framework, establishing its own decision-making process. It aims to collect feedback and monitor adoption spread among living labs across in various living lab domains. Principal responsibility of the WG is to actively engage the Living Lab community in activities towards the adoption and updating of the framework. The activities of the WG will be open to the public and will be disseminated through the ENoLL network.

3.8.2. Scaling up across domains

The Harmonization Framework presented in this document has been developed starting with the Health and Wellbeing domain and some parts include information that are applicable only to this domain. However, the Harmonization of Living Lab processes and tools is a challenge that should be extended to other domains as well. One of the goals of the Harmonization WG is also to extend the existing Living Lab Harmonization framework to diverse domains. VITALISE has also established collaborations and signed Letter of Intent with Living Labs operating in other domains such as Soil, Gender innovation, Climate to adopt and extend the VITALISE Harmonization framework.

3.8.3. Implementation of KPIs

The work done within the VITALISE project resulted in the development of 34 general Living Lab KPIs and the development of a self-assessment survey for Living Labs is being validated beyond the scope of the Vitalise project via:

1

The implementation of the self-assessment survey into the certification process of ENoLL to assess incoming applications for membership of the network.

2

The implementation of the self-assessment survey into the benchmarking process of ENoLL to benchmark their current members.

3

The KPIs and the self-assessment survey are being used as a base for the development of a self-assessment tool for Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses within the SOILL start-up project.

4

The self-assessment survey is used as assessment tool for the Living Labs within the Water-Mining project.

5

The self-assessment survey will be used as assessment tool for the Living Labs within the Rewaise project.

6

The self-assessment survey will be used as assessment tool for the Living Labs within the oPEN Lab project.

7

The KPIs will be used to support proposal writing for future projects concerning evaluation tasks of Living Labs by ENoLL.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the Living Lab Harmonization framework that was developed during the VITALISE project and provides the guidelines for using this framework. This document can be used both by Living Lab practitioners working in established Living Labs, aiming to assist on following harmonized procedures as well as by researchers that are interested in utilizing Living Lab services for their research. It provides information about the key elements of the Harmonization Framework, the developed tools and how it can be used and also addresses the sustainability plan through the uptake of the ENoLL network.

4. CONCLUSIONS

THE CONSORTIUM

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

AUTHORS

Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Giulia Campodonico (ENoLL)
Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)	Martina Desole (ENoLL)
Koen Vervoort (ENoLL)	Panagiotis Bamidis (AUTH)
Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	Silia Petronikolou (AUTH)

SPECIAL THANKS TO

ThessAHALL, LiCalab, Laurea, MindLab, Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab, GAIA Living Lab, LifeSTech, McGill UdeM CRIR, AIT

DESIGN

Penrose-CDB (penrose-cdb.com)

-
- www.vitalise-project.eu
 - [company/VITALISE-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/VITALISE-project)
 - [@VITALISEproject](https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject)
 - [Vitalise Project](https://www.facebook.com/Vitalise-Project)